

CF4J 2.0: Adapting Collaborative Filtering for Java to New Challenges of Collaborative Filtering based Recommender Systems

F. Ortega, J. Mayor, D. López-Fernández, R. Lara-Cabrera

Dpto. Sistemas Informáticos, ETSI Sistemas Informáticos, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

Abstract

CF4J 2.0 is a framework for conducting research experiments based on collaborative filtering. This framework has been designed keeping the scientific community in mind. It includes major features such as a high number of implemented algorithms from the state-of-the-art, several quality measures and parallel execution of the techniques, as well as abstract classes and interfaces to allow developers to extend and customize the library. Furthermore, this new version of the library focuses on the following key features: simple deployment of collaborative filtering experiments, reproducible science, hyper-parameter optimization, data analysis, and openness to the community as an open-source project.

Keywords: Collaborative Filtering, Recommender System, Matrix Factorization

1. Introduction

In today's information society, people are constantly dealing with the problem of information overload. We produce and consume a huge amount of data [1], so it becomes mandatory to be able to filter out the relevant information. That is, precisely, the motivation of a Recommender System (RS): passing the relevant information to the user and blocking the irrelevant one [2].

The most popular implementation of a RS is Collaborative Filtering (CF), which is capable of building recommendations based on the ratings that users assigned to a set of items. CF might follow two approaches: model-based or memory-based. The first approach builds the recommendations using a model derived from the ratings, whereas the second one uses similarity metrics to obtain the distance between two users or items according to their corresponding ratings. Performance of the CF RSs can also be improved by analyzing the users' comments with sentiment analysis techniques [3, 4]

Collaborative Filtering for Java (CF4J) is a framework to carry out CF based research experiments that were designed keeping the scientific community in mind. Although its first version had some interesting features [5], the library was developed with a strong focus on memory-based approaches, as that was widely used at that time in this field of research. However, this situation has changed and model-based approaches have gained greater relevance, as we will explain in the following section. Therefore, we have performed a full re-design and re-implementation of the library to adapt CF4J to the current state-of-the-art.

2. Problems and Background

As stated before, memory-based approaches were in vogue in the scientific community at the time the first version of the library was developed. We performed a bibliometric analysis to study the evolution in the use of both memory-based and model-based approaches. This analysis collected the number of research papers published over the last 10 years which used either a model-based or a memory-based CF technique. We chose k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN) [6] and Matrix Factorization (MF) [7] as the most representative algorithms of memory-based and model-based techniques, respectively.

Figure 1: Yearly relative frequency of kNN (model-based) and MF (memory-based) published papers.

Absolute frequencies of papers were gathered from the results obtained after querying the Scopus database of peer-reviewed literature with the following thesaurus:

Memory-based : COLLABORATIVE FILTERING AND

(NEIGHBOR **OR** NEIGHBORHOOD **OR** SIMILARITY
OR KNN)

Model-based : COLLABORATIVE FILTERING **AND**
(MATRIX FACTORIZATION **OR** LATENT **OR** FACTORS)

As it is depicted in Fig. 1, the number of kNN papers have been decreasing over the last ten years, while MF shows an increasing trend. Furthermore, a deep analysis of the emerging trends in RS research reinforces the current popularity of model-based versus memory-based ones: Li et al. [8] use binary code learning to build as the input of a neural network to better learn both user and item representations; Bobadilla et al. [9] propose a deep learning framework based on a novel representation of users rating vector to train a dense neural network whose output contains the probability that each item is of interest to the user; and Angulo et al. [10] present a special issue to address the inclusion of cognitive components into RS models.

The current popularity of model-based CF versus traditional memory-based CF motivates a complete re-design and re-implementation of CF4J. This re-implementation has been addressed keeping in mind the main driver of CF4J (i.e., conducting scientific experiments in the field of RSs) because it is the distinguishing factor of CF4J against other libraries for RSs and it is the main reason to encourage its existence and maintenance.

In Java, the programming language used to encode CF4J, there are two main libraries designed to provide recommendations using CF: *LibRec* [11] and *Mahout* [12]. An in-depth comparison between CF4J and these two libraries are included in the original publication of CF4J [5]. It concludes that: “*LibRec and Mahout are great CF libraries, but they have been designed for production environments rather than for research environments. [...] LibRec is a great library if you need a fast RS deployment due to the wide variety of recommendation methods that provides, and Mahout is the best library if you need a high scalable RS.*”

There are other software libraries, coded in languages beyond Java, devoted to RSs:

- (a) *Surprise* [13] is a popular Python library for building and analyzing RSs that deals with explicit rating data. It was designed trying to give users perfect control over their experiments, alleviate the pain of dataset handling, provide various ready-to-use prediction algorithms and make it easy to implement and evaluate new algorithm ideas and provide tools to evaluate. These features are very similar to the ones provided by CF4J and its main difference is the programming language in which they are encoded.
- (b) *Case Recommender* [14] implements several popular recommendation algorithms for both implicit and explicit feedback that aim to provide a rich set of components useful to construct a customized RS from a set of algorithms. Its documentation is poor and

it is not easy to implement new algorithm ideas as scientific software requires.

- (c) *Spotlight* [15] is a popular Python library that uses PyTorch to build different types of RS. It provides various representation techniques, loss functions and data set generation utilities. Its main difference compared to CF4J is that *Spotlight* has been specifically designed to deal with deep recommendation models.
- (d) *recommenderlab* [16] is an R library which provides an infrastructure to test and develop recommender algorithms, supporting explicit ratings (e.g., 1-5 stars) and unary (0-1) datasets. It provides good performance but its usage is not easy due to the lack of documentation and the low abstraction of its interface.

As stated before, CF4J has been built for scientific purpose and all its features and functionalities are focused to facilitate the experimentation at the frontier of knowledge of RSs. This goal is not common in software development and it makes CF4J unique.

3. Software Framework

During the re-design and re-implementation of CF4J, special attention has been paid to its ease of use and understanding. The new architecture and functionalities are described in this section.

3.1. Software Architecture

Fig. 2 contains a summarized class diagram that shows the architecture followed to design CF4J. As it can be observed, classes are distributed along with several packages according to their functionalities.

The package `data` includes all the features regarding data loading and management. That package’s main classes are `Dataset` and `DataModel`. They are responsible for loading and efficiently storing information, respectively. Note that according to the latter, information is partitioned into `Users` and `Items` objects.

The package `recommender` is the core of the library. It contains an abstract class `Recommender`, which defines the functionality to be provided by any implementation of a RS algorithm. Within this package, specific implementations of the algorithms are assigned to three categories (i.e., packages): `knn`, `matrixFactorization` and `neural`. The full list of algorithms implemented in the library and their corresponding citation is displayed in Table 1.

Lastly, the package `qualityMeasure` includes several classes devoted to computing metrics that assess the performance of a RS. These metrics are distributed along the packages `prediction` and `recommendation`. They include those metrics used to evaluate the prediction and the recommendations made by the RS, respectively.

Figure 2: Summarized class diagram of the library, including its most relevant components.

Type	Name
User and item kNN (similarity metric)	Pearson Correlation (Constrained) [2], (Adjusted) Cosine [2], Jaccard Index [2], MSD [2], Spearman Rank [2], JSMD [17], CJMSD [18], Singularities [19], PIP [20]
Matrix Factorization	BiasedMF [7], BNMF [21], CLiMF [22], HPF [23], NMF [24], PMF [25], SVD++ [26], URP [27]
Neural Networks	NCCF [9]

Table 1: Recommendation algorithms implemented in CF4J

3.2. Software Functionalities

As previously stated, the CF4J library has been designed and implemented keeping the research community in mind; hence all its functionality has a strong focus towards scientific experimentation. This new major version of the library keeps its strong scientific focus and includes the following entirely new functionalities.

3.2.1. Simple deployment of CF experiments

Ease of use is a determining factor when choosing a software tool for conducting experiments. Therefore, the library was fully re-designed and re-implemented in order to simplify the process of performing research experiments, as well as the subsequent analysis of the obtained results. Each element of the library inherits from an abstract class depending on its functionality. In this way, there is a common Application Programming Interface (API) for the different phases of the experimentation: **DataSet** interface is an abstract representation of a dataset; **DataModel** is the data structure that contains the rating matrix loaded from a **DataSet**; the **Recommender** class symbolizes any CF-based recommendation model; and **QualityMeasure** allows the definition of multiple measures to evaluate a **Recommender**.

3.2.2. Reproducible Science

Reproducible Science [28] has become a hot topic over the last years. The scientific community needs that the

published results can be corroborated by repeating the experiments that led to those scientific results. To comply with reproducibility standards, all methods using Pseudo-random number generators (PRNGs) can receive a seed as a parameter. Thus, several independent runs of the same experiment which has been set up with the same seeds will give the same results.

In addition, the most popular datasets used in CF research (MovieLens [29], FilmTrust, BookCrossing [30], Jester [31], LibimSeTi [32], MyAnimeList and Netflix Prize [33]) are preloaded into CF4J and they can be instantiated using **BenchmarkDataModels** class. In this manner, researchers interested in using the library to conduct their experiments and to be able to compare results can use the same datasets as other researchers due to the library’s capability to conduct easily reproducible experiments.

3.2.3. Hyper-parameter optimization

Due to the importance of optimizing hyper-parameters in the experimentation of machine learning algorithms, the library offers the possibility of performing this process through grid search. This method consists of an exhaustive search guided by the measure of quality. The search is performed through a manually specified subset of the hyper-parametric space of a learning algorithm. In this way, CF4J has a utility class, **GridSearch**, to perform a grid search over a **Recommender** instance by using the ranges for the hyper-parameters specified by the user.

The grid search is executed in such a way that it minimizes or maximizes a `QualityMeasure` instance.

3.2.4. Data and results analysis

In addition to obtain the results of the experiments through data files (i.e., CSV), the new version of CF4J features a module capable of generating figures from the experimental results. It makes it easier for users to compare and analyze the results obtained in their experiments. Section 5 includes some samples of the figures the library is capable of plotting.

3.2.5. Open to the community

Lastly, we concentrated our efforts during the redesign of the library on making it as open to the community as possible. As an open-source project, the GitHub repository is fully available for other developers to extend and improve the library. We hope that the new software architecture will encourage other colleagues to send their comments and pull requests to evolve and improve CF4J.

4. Implementation and Empirical Results

CF4J is a Java library designed for scientific research on CF. Therefore, its implementation focuses on usability and experimentation, while maintaining an adequate efficiency of the computations. The library includes a `Partible` interface to improve the running time. This interface adapts every step of a CF algorithm so they can be executed in parallel. The execution of those steps is carried out by the class `Parallelizer`. Note that parallelization can be executed over any array of objects, such as users, items, and their respective test splits.

Figure 3: Activity diagram of Probabilistic Matrix Factorization (PMF) algorithm, as implemented in CF4J

Most of the algorithms included in the library implements the `Partible` interface to make use of the parallelization capabilities. Fig. 3 contains an illustrative example of how the `Partible` interface is used to parallelize PMF [25] algorithm. In this case, `UpdateUsersFactors` and `UpdateItemsFactors` implement `Partible` interface, so they consist of three steps:

1. `BeforeRun` is executed once before the parallelization. It is used to initialize resources.
2. `Run` is executed once for each object in a parallel manner. `UpdateUsersFactors` executes `Run` step for each user and updates their factors. In the same way, `UpdateItemsFactors` executes `Run` step for each item and updates their factors.
3. `AfterRun` is executed once after the parallelization. It is used to close and free up resources.

The aforementioned interface has been designed to simplify the parallelization process to any researcher that wants to extend the library with another algorithm.

5. Illustrative Examples

Next, some use cases are presented in order to illustrate the key features of the library already described in Section 3.2. More complex examples can be found on GitHub's project page.

5.1. Analysis of the distribution of the votes

This example analyzes the distribution of the ratings in a dataset. This preliminary analysis may shed light on the voting dynamics that users have followed or detect any bias towards a particular rating.

```

1  DataModel datamodel = BenchmarkDataModels.MovieLens1M();
2
3  Map<String, Integer> count = new HashMap<>();
4  for (User user : datamodel.getUsers()) {
5      for (int pos = 0; pos < user.getNumberOfRatings(); pos++) {
6          double rating = user.getRatingAt(pos);
7          String key = String.valueOf(rating);
8          int num = count.containsKey(key) ? count.get(key) : 0;
9          count.put(key, num+1);
10     }
11 }
12
13 PlotSettings.setyAxisInset(125).setyAxisLabelDistance(3.1);
14
15 ColumnPlot plot = new ColumnPlot("Rating value", "Number of
16 ↪ ratings")
17     .addColumn("1.0", count.get("1.0"))
18     .addColumn("2.0", count.get("2.0"))
19     .addColumn("3.0", count.get("3.0"))
20     .addColumn("4.0", count.get("4.0"))
21     .addColumn("5.0", count.get("5.0"));
22 plot.draw();
23 plot.exportPlot("exports/column-plot.png");

```

The above code begins with the creation of a `DataModel` containing the `MovieLens1M` dataset, which is built-in in the library. Note that it is possible to load

that dataset with a single instruction (line 1). All users are then iterated and their ratings are easily counted thanks to the methods provided by `DataModel` (lines 3–11). Finally, the plotting capabilities of `CF4J` are used to represent the distribution of the ratings as a column plot (line 21) which, in turn, is saved to a file (line 22). The plot generated by this example is depicted in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Distribution of the ratings in MovieLens1M as plotted by `CF4J`.

5.2. Comparing two recommenders

This example makes a comparison between two recommenders, which is quite common in both the scientific and industrial fields. For example, a new recommendation model usually needs to be compared with other existing models to evaluate its contribution regarding the state-of-the-art. It may also be necessary to make a comparison between several RSs to analyze their performance in order to choose the most appropriate one to solve a given problem.

```

1 DataModel datamodel = BenchmarkDataModels.MovieLens1M();
2
3 int[] numberOfRecommendations = {1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9,
  ↳ 10};
4
5 LinePlot plot = new LinePlot(numberOfRecommendations, "Number
  ↳ of recommendations", "F1");
6
7 PMF pmf = new PMF(datamodel,10, 50, 43);
8 pmf.fit();
9 plot.addSeries("PMF");
10
11 for (int N : numberOfRecommendations) {
12     F1 f1 = new F1(pmf, N, 4.0);
13     double score = f1.getScore();
14     plot.setValue("PMF", N, score);
15 }
16
17 NMF nmf = new NMF(datamodel, 10, 50, 43);
18 nmf.fit();
19 plot.addSeries("NMF");
20
21 for (int N : numberOfRecommendations) {
22     F1 f1 = new F1(nmf, N, 4.0);
23     double score = f1.getScore();
24     plot.setValue("NMF", N, score);
25 }
26
27 plot.draw();

```

The above code performs a comparison between the performance of two recommenders called PMF [25] and Non-negative Matrix Factorization (NMF) [24]. Both recommenders are evaluated using the *MovieLens1M* dataset. They are compared using F1 quality measure across several values of the number of recommendations. The results of the comparison are plotted as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: F1-score over number of recommendations for two recommenders (PMF and NMF) using MovieLens1M, as plotted by `CF4J`.

5.3. Hyper-parameters tuning using grid search

As stated in Section 3.2, optimizing hyper-parameters is a crucial step in the experimentation of machine learning algorithms. This example deals with that task by using the grid search method available to optimize a BiasedMF recommender. As a result, the top 5 combinations of parameters with the lowest Mean Absolute Error (MAE) are printed out.

```

1 DataModel datamodel = BenchmarkDataModels.MovieLens100K();
2
3 ParamsGrid grid = new ParamsGrid();
4
5 grid.addParam("numIters", new int[]{50, 75, 100});
6 grid.addParam("numFactors", new int[]{5, 10, 15});
7 grid.addParam("lambda", new double[]{0.05, 0.10, 0.15});
8 grid.addParam("gamma", new double[]{0.001, 0.01, 0.1});
9
10 grid.addFixedParam("seed", 43L);
11
12 GridSearch gs = new GridSearch(datamodel, grid, BiasedMF.class,
  ↳ MAE.class);
13 gs.fit();
14 gs.printResults(5);

```

6. Conclusions

This paper presents the new version of `CF4J`, a framework to carry out CF based research experiments, that was designed keeping the scientific community in mind. The library has been fully re-designed and re-implemented from the bottom up. This new version includes major features such as a high number of implemented algorithms from

the state-of-the-art, several quality measures, and parallel execution of the algorithms. Also, the new architecture of the library allows developers to easily customize and extend the library. In addition, this new version of CF4J aims to lay the foundations of reproducible science in CF research, allowing full reproducibility of experiments and providing built-in benchmark datasets.

This paper should be read as a starting point for the use of CF4J. As a scientific software, CF4J must be evolving as science evolves. In this sense, we propose three lines of future work: (a) to extend the list of algorithms and quality measures included in the library; (b) to implement hybrid filtering methods that combine collaborative filtering with content-based or demographic filtering; and (c) to develop a graphical user interface that allows the handling of the library in a simple way for people without advanced programming skills.

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Required Metadata

Current executable software version

Ancillary data table required for the subversion of the executable software: (x.1, x.2, etc.) kindly replace examples in the right column with the correct information about your executables and leave the left column as it is.

Nr.	(executable) Software metadata description	Please fill in this column
S1	Current software version	2.1.1
S2	Permanent link to executables of this version	https://github.com/ferortega/cf4j/releases/tag/v2.1.1
S3	Legal Software License	Apache License Version 2.0
S4	Computing platform/Operating System	Linux, OS X, Microsoft Windows
S5	Installation requirements & dependencies	Java JDK 1.8 or higher
S6	If available, link to user manual - if formally published include a reference to the publication in the reference list	https://cf4j.etsisi.upm.es
S7	Support email for questions	fernando.ortega@upm.es

Table 2: Software metadata (optional)

Current code version

Ancillary data table required for the subversion of the codebase. Kindly replace examples in the right column with the correct information about your current code and leave the left column as it is.

Nr.	Code metadata description	Please fill in this column
C1	Current code version	2.1.1
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used of this code version	https://github.com/ferortega/cf4j
C3	Legal Code License	Apache License Version 2.0
C4	Code versioning system used	git
C5	Software code languages, tools, and services used	Java
C6	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Apache Commons Math 3.6.1, Apache Commons Lang 3.10, GRAL 0.11, ASCII Table 1.1.0, deeplearning4j-core 1.0.0-beta7, nd4j-native 1.0.0-beta7, slf4j-api 1.7.30, slf4j-log4j12 1.7.30
C7	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	http://cf4j.etsisi.upm.es/apidocs/v2.1.1/
C8	Support email for questions	fernando.ortega@upm.es

Table 3: Code metadata (mandatory)